

"SURGICAL TREATMENT SECONDARY FACIAL DEFORMITIES IN CREVICES UPPER LIP"

Shermatova Kamola Hamraevna

(resident of the Department of Maxillofacial region)

« Institute of Stomatology»

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13726042>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 02nd September 2024

Accepted: 06th September 2024

Online: 07th September 2024

KEYWORDS

Lip deformities, patient, surgery, oral hygiene, causes, plaque, cheiloplasty.

ABSTRACT

Many different techniques are used to eliminate lip deformity after cleft. Most often, the patient needs a set of procedures that will help him adjust his appearance. But it is worth noting that the younger the patient, the less radical the intervention. The operation is performed by an experienced surgeon.

Cheiloplasty is a plastic surgery to change (correct) the shape and size of the lips. In 90% of cases, they are performed in order to achieve cosmetic and aesthetic results, 10% account for the elimination of the consequences of injuries and birth defects. Modern techniques allow you to radically change the size of the lips, give the desired shape and volume, restore symmetry, remove wrinkles around the contour and in the corners of the mouth, correct cheiloschisis (congenital cleavage of the palate), remove benign neoplasms.

Indications for cheiloplastics age-related changes (loss of volume, the appearance of vertical wrinkles along the contour of the lips, lowering of the corners of the mouth, thinning of the skin);

dissatisfaction with one's own appearance;

cosmetic defects;

the consequences of unsuccessful plastic surgery or tattooing;

disproportionate lip volume (too large or too small);

traumatic injuries, scars and scars;

congenital anomalies;

the smooth contour of the upper lip.

Contraindications Surgical correction of the lip shape refers to minimally invasive operations, however, there are a number of contraindications for cheiloplasty:

young age (up to 18 years old, operations are performed to eliminate birth defects, the effects of injuries or pronounced imbalances);

skin diseases (infectious, fungal, parasitic);

general contraindications to surgical intervention (uncompensated diabetes mellitus, grade III hypertension, diseases of the cardiovascular system;

oncology, chronic diseases in the acute stage, etc.);

mental abnormalities.

The degree of risk in the presence of contraindications is assessed by the attending physician, after which a decision is made on the possibility of surgery. You should not try to hide your existing health problems: this can lead to tragic consequences. Types of cheiloplasty There are more than 20 types of lip defects in plastic surgery, but all of them are successfully corrected using five recognized and proven techniques:

Shortening

It is recommended for disproportionate lip length (upper or lower). Shortening is achieved by removing an ellipsoid-shaped flap of the mucous membrane from the inside of the lip.

V-Y plastic

The essence of the correction is to move the mucosa outwards. With the help of V-shaped incisions on the inside of the lips, the mucous membrane is slightly shifted forward. After that, the incisions are sewn in the form of the letter Y. The sutures are hidden in the oral cavity and leave no traces after healing.

"Paris"

V-shaped incisions are made in both vertical and horizontal directions. The technique allows you to increase the volume of lips of any shape.

Corner elevator

The operation eliminates age-related changes (vertical wrinkles along the contour, drooping corners of the mouth, loss of skin elasticity). The essence of the technique is to excise the skin above the upper lip. By removing a small skin flap, the corners of the lips are pulled up, resembling a light smile.

Bulhorn

The technique is aimed at increasing the volume of the upper lip. An incision is made under the base of the nose, after which a thin strip of skin is removed. After stitching the edges of the wound, the lip rises. How is the consultation going? At the first appointment, the doctor conducts a thorough visual examination, palpates soft tissues. After clarifying the patient's complaints and wishes, the tactics of surgical intervention are determined. Often, women with minor problems turn to a plastic surgeon, which can be corrected by alternative non-surgical methods: in this case, the doctor will try to convince the patient not to resort to radical surgical correction. After determining the type of cheiloplasty, the surgeon tells in detail about the features of the operation, the expected results and possible risks, and also gives recommendations for rehabilitation. For the convenience of nonresident patients wishing to have cheiloplasty in Vologda, an online consultation (Viber, Skype) is provided. Preparation for surgery After making a decision on cheiloplasty, the date and time of the operation are agreed upon, then the doctor issues referrals for tests and additional examinations (if necessary). The results must be no more than 14 days old before the scheduled date. It is absolutely necessary: provide the results of fluorography; do an ECG and get a cardiologist's opinion; take a blood test (general, biochemical, for RW, hepatitis, HIV, clotting) and urine (general clinical); get expert opinions. Despite the low traumatic nature of the operation, consultation with a therapist and an anesthesiologist is required. At the CONSTANT Clinic in Vologda, cheiloplasty is usually performed under local anesthesia. Modern drugs completely block pain and have no side effects. How is the operation going? A

few days before the scheduled date, the anesthesiologist will examine the results of the tests, select an anesthesia regimen (as a rule, cheiloplasty is performed under local anesthesia). During the consultation, it is necessary to inform the doctor about the medications taken, previous illnesses and allergic reactions. In case of high emotional lability, pre-sedation is possible. Stages of the operation Preparatory You must come to the Clinic strictly on the appointed day. After being placed in a comfortable room, you will have a meeting with a plastic surgeon and an anesthesiologist for a checkup. Next, a Clinic employee will take you to the operating room. Operation The surgical field is treated with an antiseptic solution. After anesthesia is administered and pain sensitivity is completely lost, the surgeon makes incisions according to the chosen cheiloplasty technique. To prevent bleeding, blood vessels are coagulated with a laser. The final one The incisions are sutured with the finest threads with a special cosmetic seam, which after healing does not leave scars and scars. Postoperative After the operation, which lasts 40-60 minutes, you will be transferred to a ward where you will stay for no more than an hour, after which you can go home (preferably with an accompanying person). Rehabilitation After surgery, small stitches remain on the lip (the size and quantity depend on the volume of surgery). Complete healing takes place within 2-3 weeks, and the stitches are removed on the seventh to tenth day after surgery. In order to avoid infection and for better fixation, strips of a special patch are applied to the suture area. Do not panic because of swelling and redness - in the first days after cheylopdasty, this is considered the norm. The blood supply to the lip tissues is characterized by high intensity, which accelerates healing. Cool compresses, lip protection from mechanical irritation and thermal effects will help to avoid complications. A month after the operation, the rehabilitation period is considered completed.

References:

1. Fattaeva, D., Muxtorov, I., Rustambekov, B., & Polotxanov, M. (2023). EVALUATION OF CLINICAL EXAMINATION RESULTS. POST-OPERATIVE CONDITIONS. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(5), 213-216.
2. Fattayeva, D., Xoliqov, A., & Yusupova, I. (2023). FEATURES OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF WISE TOOTH PERICORONITIS. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(7), 10-14.
3. Alimurodovich, K. A., Rustamovna, F. D., Abrorjonovich, S. E., & Hamraevna, S. K. (2023). Materials and methods of clinical research. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 20, 73-76.
4. Fattayeva, Dilorom, Eldor Shermatov, and Kamola Shermatova. "THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE TREATMENT OF ABSCESSSES AND PHLEGMON USING CHLORHEXIDINE." *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research* 3.5 (2023): 161-164.
5. Alimurodovich, Khalikov Azizbek, and Rakhmatov Jakhongir Bakhodirovich. "COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF MFR PLASTIC OPERATIONS." *American Journal of Technology and Applied Sciences* 7 (2022): 34-38.

6. Фаттаева, Д. Р., Ризаев, Ж. А., Рахимова, Д. А., & Холиков, А. А. (2021). CLINICAL PICTURE OF SINUSITIS IN PATIENTS AFTER COVID-19 WITH CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE. УЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ, 2(2).
7. Urunbaeva, S. S., Alishakhi, L. S., Pirmatov, M. A., & Fattayeva, D. R. (2022). OPTIMIZATION OF TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH PHLEGMON OF THE MAXILLOFACIAL REGION. British View, 7(4).
8. Mamadrizaeva, Z. F., Rakhmatova, S. S., Yunusov, A. A., & Fattayeva, D. R. (2022). FEATURES OF THE TREATMENT OF FRACTURES OF THE ZYGOMATIC-ORBITAL COMPLEX. British View, 7(4).
9. Urunbaeva, S. S., Pirmatov, M. A., Nosirov, S. S., & Kholikov, A. A. (2022). COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE TREATMENT OF MANDIBULAR FRACTURES. British View, 7(4).
10. Olimjonov, T. A., Fattayeva, D. R., & Umarov, J. A. (2022). Treatment methods for fractures of the zygomatic-orbital complex. Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities, 13, 65-68.
11. Shamov, V. V., Kholikov, A. A., & Fattayeva, D. R. (2022). Improvement of treatment methods of combined traumas of maxillofacial region. Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities, 13, 56-61.
12. Холмурадов, Ж. Р., Холиков, А. А., & Фаттаева, Д. Р. (2022). МЕТОДЫ ОБСЛЕДОВАНИЯ БОЛЬНЫХ С ФЛЕГМОНАМИ ЧЕЛЮСТНОЛИЦЕВОЙ ОБЛАСТИ. Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS), 2(12), 97-101.
13. Alimurodovich, K. A., & Rustamovna, F. D. (2023). Differential Diagnosis of Facial Pain. Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies, 2(4), 36-42.